

Entropic Ecstasy: On the Commodification of Entropy

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Typical sequences have higher entropy than rare, atypical ones. In their race to become more consumable, AI chatbots produce higher and higher entropy artifacts. This makes them appear more and more credible. However, it also makes them diverge from what is normal or even high entropy in human (non-AI) artifact space.

We ran a simple experiment comparing a natural image, an artwork and an AI generated image and found the natural image to have the lowest entropy and the AI generated image to have the highest. We then ran the experiment on text, comparing a 19th century English author, a modern scientific author (no AI use) and scientific text generated using AI. Again we found the 19th century author to have the lowest entropy and the AI generated scientific text to have the highest entropy.

These are single run experiments and therefore not statistically rigorous. Nevertheless, they are suggestive. We encourage everyone to run such experiments and see for themselves, how the AI companies are selling them "entropy."